

EFFECTIVE BUSINESS COMMUNICATION – MAKES ONE SUCCESSFUL

S. Gomathy

Assistant Professor, AMET University, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

The Oxford English Dictionary (2005) defines language as “Words and the methods of combining them for the expression of thought.” When the thought is rightly expressed and understood, it results in successful communication. Communication, as everyone knows is the sharing of ideas, knowledge and thoughts. In a business the end point or goal is getting profit. To have profit, the product has to be made, marketed and the money is to be recovered. It includes human interaction in a wider range. Communication is present between the Employer and employee, manager and staff and among the work force. How to run a successful business? How to be an effective and a winning communicator in business world is the focus of the paper.

Key Words: Communication, Human Interaction, Successful Business, Profit & Winning Communication

Introduction:

Today’s world is a fast growing one where people have multiple responsibilities and many roles to play with. Human life is interesting because of communication. Verbal communication makes the world lively and vibrant. In today’s world, with almost universal trade and business practices, communication has acquired a prominent place which it has not assumed before. Communication is central to all the activities of the society. Communication becomes purposive. G.T.Vardaman opines that “communication is a purposive symbolic interchange, resulting in workable understanding and agreement between the sender and the receiver”. So professionalism reflects in effective communication.

Communication in an Organization:

In an organization / company, both internal and external communication takes place. Internal is between the MD and the staff or between department heads, or among staff. External communication takes place between the company and the customers, bankers, mass media, between government departments and the general public. Every company receives inward communication from public, other companies, government and regulatory bodies.

What are the Needed Qualities of Business Communication?

Any business related communication has any one of these three important functions:

- ✓ To Inform
- ✓ To Persuade
- ✓ To Promote Goodwill

Interpersonal skill plays a major role in achieving it. When passing on information, the words chosen by the speaker is very important. The tone of the speaker is equally important. The speaker’s words and tone should reflect the intention of the communication. To get a positive response the words must be pleasing, persuading and informative. The intended information should reach the receiver as it is desired to be.

Strategies for Effective Communication:

- ✓ Involving Every One
- ✓ Arousing and Sustaining Interest
- ✓ Listening Intently
- ✓ Developing Ideas Adequately
- ✓ Paraphrasing the Message
- ✓ Reflecting Emotions
- ✓ Reflecting Implications
- ✓ Inviting Further Contribution
- ✓ Showing Appropriate Non Verbal Signals
- ✓ Using Right Tone

When these are rightly incorporated the speaker’s message is absorbed in the right sense and results in intended reaction / feedback. Avoiding redundancy is also very much needed to have the interest of the listeners and retain their attention. Being brief and sweet is more essential in communication. Choosing the right diction and selective usage of them will result positive. Conversational skill enables our business meetings to be pay - off and our social gathering to become more rewarding. Having a good conversational skill is a magic key to professional success and social popularity. An effective speaker has two main concerns to be successful - content and delivery. When the content is self sufficient and self explanatory it helps the speaker. The mode of delivery and the word power of the speaker are important.

Communication Barriers:

- ✓ Perceptual and Language Differences
- ✓ Information Overload
- ✓ Inattention
- ✓ Time Pressures
- ✓ Distraction/Noise
- ✓ Complexity in Organizational Structure
- ✓ Emotions
- ✓ Poor retention

How to Overcome These Barriers of Communication?

To eliminate language differences, proper induction training is to be given. The information should be in simple language avoiding jargons.

- ✓ Holding listener's attention is very important.
- ✓ Giving feedback and accepting from the workers about the company is also important.(Two way feedback)
- ✓ Tell the truth
- ✓ Know your audience and focus on your communication accordingly
- ✓ Use appropriate body language which influences a lot
- ✓ Using multi channel and frequent communication is effective.

Effects of Good Business Communication:

- ✓ Helps to deal with cultural, cadre diversity
- ✓ Increases Global Business
- ✓ Helps in Team Building
- ✓ Improves Employee Morale

Effective verbal and nonverbal communication skills are valuable in the workplace. Some companies spend a lot of money to train their employees on how to communicate effectively. Good communication skills go beyond conversations, but employees must know how to communicate well in written reports and emails. Understanding the benefits of effective communication helps companies place a focus on developing a workforce that is able to communicate within the firm and with customers, vendors and international business partners.

Conclusion:

As communication is vital for changes to be brought in, to accomplish the organizational goal, it is to be short and crisp. Communication works for those who work at it. - John Powell. Effective communication skill is important for achieving success- whether for motivating workers, to inform an important matter, share ideas, to give feedback etc- in short to achieve what is intended. The brilliant ideas you have will not take you to success unless it is shared successfully with effective communication. Communication skill is important for all especially for business people to be successful in business.

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